

Synthesis and characterization of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} substituted polytungstates and molybdates

K. C. Dey^{*a} and V. Sharma^b

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Jamshedpur Cooperative College, Jamshedpur-831 001, Jharkhand, India

E-mail : kdehy_ru@rediffmail.com

^bDepartment of Chemistry, RVS College of Engineering and Technology, Jamshedpur-831 012, Jharkhand, India

Manuscript received 28 April 2008, revised 21 July 2008, accepted 1 August 2008

Abstract : Two sodium salts of mixed heteropoly oxometalates of tungstate and molybdate with the molecular formula $\text{Na}_{10}[\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{Ni}^{\text{II}}\text{W}^{\text{VI}}_{11}\text{O}_{40}]\cdot 21\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (1) and $\text{Na}_{10}[\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{Ni}^{\text{II}}\text{Mo}^{\text{VI}}_{11}\text{O}_{40}]\cdot 20\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (2) having Keggin type anion $[\text{X}^{\text{x}+}\text{Z}^{\text{z}+}\text{W}_{11}\text{O}_{40}]^{-}$ ($14-\text{x}-\text{z}$) have been synthesized. The compounds were prepared by hydrothermal method from aqueous acidic solution of reagents. The resulting compounds were characterized by elemental and thermal analyses, IR studies and molecular weight determination.

Keywords : Polyanion of tungstate, Ni substituted POM, molybdonickelate, tungstonickelate.

Introduction

Polyoxometalates are complexes those can be described either 'top-down', as discrete fragments of metallic oxides or 'bottom up' as condensed oxo complexes. They are rich and growing class of inorganic compounds¹⁻³ with interest both for their possible applications⁴ and for their usefulness as model to understand the electronic properties of metal oxide at the molecular level. Their excellent properties related to functional materials such as catalysis, electronic, magnetism and medicine have been quite attractive⁵. In particular, the electronic and magnetic diversity have been studied theoretically⁶ for the polytungstates and molybdates. This arises both from their ability to host delocalized electrons⁷ and from their aptitude to encapsulate clusters of magnetic transition metal ions which isolate them from the rest of the ions of the crystal. A common synthetic strategy for the preparation of transition metal substituted polyoxometalates involves the reaction of a transition metal with the polydentate ligand formed by the self assembly⁸. The giant leap of polyoxometalate chemistry is largely depended upon the progress for the Keggin and related structures having tetrahedral heteroatom. The progress for the compounds containing octahedral heteroatom has been slower. Transition metal substituted polyoxotungstates based on the Keggin framework have received considerable attention^{9,10}

and have been synthesized and studied widely. Baker and his co-workers¹¹ first described the anion of the type $[\text{X}^{\text{x}+}\text{Z}^{\text{z}+}\text{W}_{11}\text{O}_{40}\text{H}_n]^{-(14-\text{x}-\text{z}-n)}$ in which one tungsten atom of the Keggin¹² anion $[\text{X}^{\text{x}+}\text{W}_{12}\text{O}_{40}]^{-(8-\text{x})}$ has been replaced by a Z atom (usually from the first transition series). The position of the transition metal atoms in these anions is always disordered and their location could not be determined accurately as previously reported transition metal substituted discrete units¹³ or in one dimensional polyoxometalates¹⁴. The majority of investigations are devoted to the applications of the Keggin type heteropoly acids (HPAs) and their salts. The Keggin POMs are attractive oxidation catalysts^{15,16} due to some of their unique properties such as metal oxide like structure, thermal and hydrolytic stability, tunability of acid, redox properties and solubility in various media.

In the present work, the hydrothermal synthesis and spectroscopic characterization of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} substituted polyoxotungstates and molybdates of the Keggin type POMs have been reported.

Results and discussion

Due to wide applications in the field of POMs, the hydrothermal process has been used for preparation of the large number of novel organic and inorganic solid state materials. The experiments were carried out in a

Table 1. Infrared spectra of the heteropoly compounds

Compd.	IR assignment (cm ⁻¹)				
	vOH	v(Cu-O)	v(Ni-O)	v(M-O)	v(M-O-M)
Na ₁₀ [Cu ^{II} Ni ^{II} W ^{VI} ₁₁ O ₄₀].21H ₂ O (1)	3460	570m	985s	1631s	767b
		530m	940s	1410s	810s
		510s	910b	1125m,b	
Na ₁₀ [Cu ^{II} Ni ^{II} Mo ^{VI} ₁₁ O ₄₀].20H ₂ O (2)	3510	565s	990m	1050s,b	772
		535m	960b	1000s	815m
		515s	955s	950s	

M = W for compound (1) and Mo for compound (2).

one pot containing copper chloride, nickel chloride and sodium salts of tungstate or molybdate for the synthesis of the compounds (1) and (2), respectively. The complexes are soluble in water and are thermodynamically stable. The analyses of the constituent elements of (1) and (2) from ICPAES are as follows : [Na, 6.7; Cu, 1.9; Ni, 1.8; W, 61.1; O, 18.22% (by diff.)]. Calcd. for Na₁₀[Cu^{II}Ni^{II}W^{VI}₁₁O₄₀].21H₂O (1) [Na, 6.8; Cu, 1.84; Ni, 1.7; W, 60.29; O, 18.56% (by diff.)] and [Na, 9.9; Cu, 2.6; Ni, 2.7; Mo, 43.8; O, 26.5% (by diff.)]. Calcd. for Na₁₀[Cu^{II}Ni^{II}Mo^{VI}₁₁O₄₀].20H₂O (2) [Na, 9.6; Cu, 2.6; Ni, 2.4; Mo, 43.3; O, 26.2% (by diff.)] respectively.

The IR spectra (Table 1) show the peaks in the range of 1631–950 cm⁻¹ which can be attributed to v(W-O) and v(Mo-O) stretching vibration for compounds (1) and (2), respectively. The sharp peak at 815–767 cm⁻¹ may be due to W-O-W and Mo-O-Mo bridge vibration¹⁷. The small but sharp band at 570–510 cm⁻¹ depicts the presence of Cu-O bond in the Keggin complex. The molecular vibration at 990–910 cm⁻¹ shows the presence of Ni-O bond in the distorted octahedral complex. The broad band at 3510–3460 cm⁻¹ indicates the lattice water molecules¹⁸. The stretching of the peripheral water molecules in compound (2) at 3510 cm⁻¹ represents a small deviation from the compound (1) which is at 3460 cm⁻¹.

The thermal analyses of both the heteropoly salts showed characteristics endothermic peaks which correspond to dehydration. The curves depict the dehydration of the compounds in two steps.

For compound (1), the residual amount in the first step is 80% from 25–200 °C and that for the second step is 67% from 200–265 °C.

For compound (2), the amount left in the first stage is 78% from 25–200 °C and that for the second step is 65% from 200–265 °C. No further attempts were made to

identify the final insoluble oxides.

Ni and Cu act as heteroatoms which probably occupy the tetrahedral or octahedral void by replacing tungsten or molybdenum atom from the Keggin complex. The apparent molecular weight of the compounds (1) and (2) have been found 3350.2 and 2311.2 as determined by cryoscopic method using Na₂SO₄.10H₂O-water system as solvent¹⁹ against calculated molecular weight of 3454.2 and 2413.2, respectively.

Experimental

The reactants were used as purchased without further purification. The solutions were freshly prepared using distilled water.

EI digital pH meter was used for the record of the activity of hydrogen ion in the solution. The elemental analyses of sodium, copper, nickel, tungsten and molybdenum were carried out by inductively coupled plasma atomic emission spectrometry (Jobin Yvon France of model JY Ultima-2) at IIT, Powai. The infrared spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 577 FT-IR spectrometer. The samples were grounded with dry KBr and pressed into transparent disks for recording infrared spectra (4400–450 cm⁻¹). Thermal analyses were carried out on a Perkin-Elmer TGA-DTA instrument, under nitrogen flow, with a heating rate of 10 °C/min. The molecular weight was determined by cryoscopic method using Beckmann's thermometer.

Synthesis of 11-Tungsto nickel cuprate(II) oxometalate :

The compound was synthesized by refluxing stoichiometric amount of Na₂WO₄.2H₂O, CuCl₂.2H₂O and NiCl₂.6H₂O in a molar ratio of 65 : 6 : 6.

10 g of copper chloride was dissolved in the 30 ml of the water and was mixed with 30 ml solution containing 1.0 g of nickel chloride. Glacial acetic acid (10 ml) was added to it in order to maintain the acidic environment^{14,15}.

The above mixture was added to the sodium tungstate solution (21.28 g in 70 ml distilled water) dropwise till a constant pH. After the addition of the 52 ml of the mixture, constancy in pH at 4.31 was found which indicated the formation of complex. An acidic buffer tablet of pH 4 was dropped into the final reaction mixture. The mixture was digested for 3 h, filtered and the filtrate was left for crystallization at room temperature for one day. The blue crystals were separated out which were washed with *n*-hexane and dried for analysis.

Synthesis of the II-Molybdo nickel cuprate(II) oxometalate :

The stoichiometric amount of Na₂MoO₄·2H₂O, CuCl₂·2H₂O and NiCl₂·6H₂O in a molar ratio of 65 : 6 : 6 were refluxed. Synthetic procedure was similar to the tungstate complex.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the SAIF, IIT, Powai for the result of elemental analyses. One of the authors (V.S.) is thankful to the Director, RVSCET, JSR for providing the resources for the synthetic work.

References

1. M. T. Pope, "Heteropoly and Isopoly Oxometalates", Springer, Berlin, 1983.
2. S. K. Roy and K. C. Dey, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1991, **68**, 461.
3. S. K. Roy and K. C. Dey, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1992, **31**, 64.
4. M. T. Pope and A. Mullar, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1991, **30**.
5. L. C. W. Baker and J. S. Figgis, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1970, **92**, 3794.
6. J. M. Maestre, J. M. Poblet, C. Bo, N. C. Pastor and P. G. Romero, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1998, **37**, 3444.
7. M. Kozik, C. F. Hammer and L. C. W. Baker, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1986, **108**, 2748.
8. D. Hagrman, C. Zubieta, D. J. Rose, J. Zubieta and R. C. Haushatters, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1997, **36**, 873.
9. C. L. Hill and R. B. Brown, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1986, **108**, 536.
10. M. Faraj and C. L. Hill, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1987, 1487.
11. L. C. W. Baker, V. S. Baker, K. Eriks, M. T. Pope, M. Shibata, O. W. Rollins, J. H. Fang and L. L. Koh, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1966, **88**, 2329.
12. J. F. Keggin, *Proc. Roy. Soc. (A)*, 1934, **144**, 75.
13. U. Kortz and S. Matta, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2001, **40**, 815.
14. H. T. Evans (Jr.), T. J. R. Weakley and G. B. Jamerson, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1996, 2539.
15. C. L. Hill, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1995, **143**, 407.
16. G. A. Tsigdinos, "Topics in Current Chemistry", Springer Verlag, Berlin, Heidelberg, New York, 1978, **76**, 54.
17. D. H. Brown, *Spectrochimica Acta*, 1962, **19**, 583.
18. T. J. R. Weakly, *Structure and Bonding*, 1974, **18**, 153.
19. C. M. Flynn and M. T. Pope, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1971, **10**, 25.